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The Dynamics and Fallout of East African Community Common Market: Trade aspect and Citizens' Rights

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The establishment of East African Community Common Market in July 2010 was a positive step taken by Partner States for pursuing intra-regional trade liberalization through free movement of goods, capital, persons and services. This aimed at widening and deepening the level of co-operation among the Partner States in the economic and social fields leading to political federation. However, four years of being operational, the full implementation of the Common Market remains challenging. This paper makes a review on compliance of the Common Market Protocol while analysing progress made in the implementation process as well as examining regional prospects and challenges. The paper concludes by arguing that Partner States should re-think, plan and work together to comply with the Protocol for strong implementation in order to deliver the rights and freedom enshrined in.

Keywords: EAC, Common Market, Partner States, implementation, integration, region.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The East African Community (EAC) is not a new phenomenon in the region following its historical background, dating back from colonial times. The colonial integration system established among other things; Kenya–Uganda Railway 1897–1901, Customs Collection Centre–1900, the East African Currency Board and Postal Union–1905, to the Joint Economic Council–1940. This experience was bequeathed to the newly independent States, in a framework of the “East African Common Services Organisation” (1961–1966). Besides this, in June, 1967, the Presidents; “Julius Nyerere of Tanzania, Milton Obote of Uganda and Jomo Kenyatta of Kenya signed the East African Co-operation treaty in Kampala” (Asante and Chanaiwa, 1993) that dawned the new EAC. The Community became a real halcyon and model for African integration. As issues including, “external trade, fiscal and monetary policy, transport and communications infrastructures, and university education were all regional rather than national” (Ibid). Ten years after, the community collapsed due to unequal sharing of benefits and lack of political will among leaders.

Following the 1984 Mediation Agreement and its pledge for future co-operation, in November, 1999, the three Partner States (“the PSs”), signed the “Treaty for the Establishment of the East African Community” (“the Treaty”) that entered into force in July, 2000. This gave re-birth to two things. One is the re-birth of new–EAC and secondly, the re-birth of the East African common heritages that existed for many years ago. Therefore, it is undeniable that, regional leaders were “determined to strengthen their economic, social, cultural, political, technological and other ties for their fast balanced and sustainable development [in the region]” (EAC, 1999). This is to say, East African states were now enthusiastic to join and be joined to the community. Also, it demonstrated that, the new co-operation had new institutional framework to ensure that agreements, policies and programmes are initiated and executed effectively and efficiently to foster the co-operation and integration.

Demonstrating this in 2005, “the East African Custom Union” (“the EACU”) was established by all member states agreeing to establish a single customs territory to facilitate free movement of goods within the region (EAC, 2013; Mwapachu, 2012). In 2007, Rwanda and Burundi joined the Community. With the same motives, “the Protocol on the Establishment of the EAC Common Market” (“the Protocol/CMP”) was signed by the Heads of States on November 20th, 2009, coinciding with the 10th Anniversary celebrations of the revived Community (EAC, 2012). The Protocol entered into force on July 1st, 2010 following ratification from all PSs: Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda (EAC, 2012; Mwapachu, 2012; Mangachi, 2011; FES, 2012; World Bank (WB), 2013). Likewise, on November 30th, 2013, the summit Heads of States approved and signed the “Protocol on the Establishment of the East African Monetary Union” in which PSs agreed to conclude the ratification process by July, 2014. Thus, the

signing of the Treaty and Protocols has been greeted with optimism and high expectations, but its implementation needs a critical look. Although some achievements have been seen, regional predicaments and challenges are enormous. So far, most of the agreements remain a mirage. PSs are crawling in the implementation process than walking their talks. Instead, they have continued anchoring in compromise politics in the region thus, favouring national interest over supranational interest.

It is on this ground that, the paper intends to explore the dynamics of the EAC–Common Market (EAC–CM) by focusing de jure compliance and implementation of the CMP. The focus here is mainly on trade in goods as well as the rights of establishment and residence. Along this, the paper examines the prospects and challenges arising within. The paper is divided into six parts; part one is the introduction and part two portrays an overview of the EAC Common Market (EAC–CM). Part three covers the intra-regional trade and rights of establishment and residence dynamics. Part four examines the prospects and challenges which impede the achievement of optimistic objectives of the CMP. Also, it is from these two parts (part three and four), where the paper demonstrates the ups-and-downs of the EAC–CM by showing on how PSs have been reacting reluctantly and in retrospect while crawling to walk their talks. Part five covers possible reforms to make the EAC–CM work easily; meanwhile, the last part sums up the discussion.

2.0 EAC COMMON MARKET REVIEW

The EAC Common Market (EAC–CM) was established in accordance with Articles 76 and 104 of the Treaty. Pursuant to Article 1 of the Treaty, “Common Market” means the PSs’ markets integrated into a single market in which there is free movement of capital, goods, labour and services. The overall objective of the EAC–CM is to widen and deepen co-operation among the PSs in the economic and social fields (EAC, 2009) whereby there is regulated economic growth and sustainable development. Subsequently, under Article 3(2) of the CMP, the EAC–CM operation is guided by four principles of: non-discrimination; equal treatment; transparency and sharing of information for appropriate implementation of the Protocol. In this vein, PSs agree to create free and robust market trade in the bloc where the envisaged freedoms and rights shall be fully achieved by December, 2015. Several committees have been set up to work on realizing each of these freedoms, such as the Monetary Affairs Committee, which is overseeing the harmonization of monetary and exchange rate policies, and the Committee on Fiscal Affairs, which is in charge of the harmonization of both tax policy and administrative processes (WB, 2013).

Under this Protocol, Article 6 allows free movement to all locally produced goods within the Community. Article 7, 13 and 14 provide for the free movement of persons and the right to all East African citizens to establish residence anywhere within the Community. This means that citizens within the Community are free to move and enter any country for the purpose of living, visiting, touring, transit, education, training, and working.

Therefore, the establishment of the EAC-CM is a notable feature not only for the sub-region, but also for a region-wide initiative which forge to establish the African Economic Community (AEC) per—the 1991 Abuja Treaty. This is because, for quite a long time, there has been continued marginalization of Africa in the global economy. However, Africa’s intra-regional trade in goods remain relatively low with unconnected markets. For instance, World Economic Forum (WEF) (2013) reports, Africa “total goods exports is just 12%, compared with 25% in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), 65% in the European Union (EU), and 49% in the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) bloc in 2011.” The point here is that Africa exportation (within and outside the continent) in goods and services is relatively small, basing on primary products. This is to say that, since trade commodities remain undiversified, whenever commodity prices fluctuate, it jeopardises the African market economy. For example, in 2012, “Europe had the highest share of intra-regional trade at 75% despite Euro sluggishness, followed by Asia at 52%, then North America at 48%. Africa stood at 12.8% or US\$ 81 billion” (AFDB, OECD & UNDP, 2014). Thus, African countries have vigorously pursued an integration agenda as a collective development and transformation strategy (UNECA, 2012). To this juncture, questions remain that will the EAC meet their self-imposed deadlines and therefore, rift the region from global economic marginalization? How can they do that?

3.0 INTRA-REGIONAL TRADE WITHIN THE EAC–CM FRAMEWORK

The establishments of the EACU in 2005 and EAC-CM in 2010 have the potential to build economies of scale, accelerate competitiveness, technology diffusion, and accelerate free movement of people leading to the realization of ultimate political integration of the region. According to the *EAC Development Strategy (2011/2012–2015/2016, EAC–DS)*, “intra-EAC trade, value of total trade, exports, imports, and trade balance between PSs within the EAC region; and with the rest of the world for the period, 2005 to 2010, indicates that intra-EAC regional trade performance was growing” (EAC, 2011). This gave an impression that the EACU has been quite successful in

bolstering intra-regional trade even when there are a number of challenges that continue to afflict its enormous potential (Mwapachu, 2012). It is therefore of note, that the regional trade shares of Gross Domestic Products (GDP) has been increasing and significant since 2005 despite of the global economic crisis. In 2005 for example, the total share of region GDP (US\$ million) stood at 2218.6 before reaching 3514.1 in 2010 (EAC, 2011). This shows an average annual growth rate of 12%. Jesca Eriyo, EAC deputy secretary, productive and social sectors, recently noted that the region has combined GDP of about US\$84 billion, it is one of the fastest growing economies in Africa, with a growth rate of 3.7% between 2010 and 2012 and a growing intra-regional trade of 5%. Thus, EAC should speed up the implementation of the CMP, if we want to increase the volume and value of trade within the region. If this happens, the rationale behind the 1991 Abuja Treaty of consolidating regional economic communities (RECs) will eventually lead to the merge of robust AEC by 2028.

How do East African countries comply with trade arrangements as CMP? States negotiate on terms and rules to regulate trade flows and other associated matters. After negotiation, all states in EAC are required to ratify the agreed protocol in order to become a new legal binding instrument. After East African PSs ratified the CMP, it entered into force on July 1st, 2010. One of the reasons for this, has been to seek national consistent support from signing to adoption, ratification to domestication and finally to implementation. According to Article 5(2) of the CMP, there must be: elimination of Tariffs, Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs), and technical barriers to trade; removal of border controls; the liberalization of financial markets; the standardization of industrial regulations and product specifications; removal of restrictions on the right of establishment and residence of nationals of other PSs; the harmonization of rules of origin and Value Added Tax (VAT) and the elimination of other trade barriers– to allow full exploitation of all freedoms and rights enshrined in the CMP.

To be sure, the Partner governments agree in accordance with Article 5(3) to co-operate and co-ordinate their activities to ensure fair competition, mutual benefits, protection of cross-border investments and implement Common External Tariff (CET). However, despite these optimistic arrangements to create free intra-trade within the region, trade remains or is far from being free. The rights of establishment and residence also follow suit as some members are yet to change their immigration policies, laws and systems to that of free movement. Instead there has been de jure inconsistency and inappropriate compliance and implementation of the CMP, thus it has remained pronounced more theoretically than practiced.

After four years in operation, EAC–CM has not made concrete “Afro-EAC-optimism.” Without the author underestimating the achievement reached so far, the author sees that most of the agreements are bound to fail. PSs are yet to harmonise crucial trade policies such as East African Standards (EAS) and technical regulations, and fiscal policy to allow equal levied taxes thus, contribute trade imbalance within the region. Instead, traditional lens still exist where the national budget of PSs is ready one day and at the same time, that existed before signing of EACM. Nevertheless, there is much variation on the ease of paying taxes and different taxes charged: VAT, exercise duty and income tax. To point a few instances, according to *Doing Business in EAC*, Rwanda requires 17 payments a year while Burundi, Uganda, Kenya, and Tanzania require 25, 31, 41 and 48 payments respectively (WB, 2013) while doing business. In July 2013, Kenya Association of Manufacturers (KAM) reported that there were still arbitrary protectionist measures that are undermining the EAC–CM (Wahome, 2013). It claimed that Uganda and Tanzania are increasingly charging full duty on imports from Kenya contrary to Article 25 of the EACU. Similar instances have also been reported by other enterprises in the region. Tanzania Cement Producers, for example, in September, 2013 called for the government to reinstate the EACU 2005 in order to ensure steady supply of cement and an equal level of playing field in the market (Domasa, 2013). This emerged following unequal statutory taxes and duties paid by cement firms in Tanzania while under the EACU, all imported cement are subjected to 55% statutory taxes and duties where 25% is for CET and 30% is for duties yet, some traders were believed to be paying less than 10% duties (Ibid). Therefore, in reference to the above observations, EAC–CM is still threatened by unfair competition, different standards and variation charges of CET, duties, Tariffs and NTBs that makes the intra-regional trade and market far from being free, equal and competitive as anticipated.

The recent research, “*EAC Common Market Scorecard 2014*” that was conducted by the EAC Secretariat, the PSs Representatives and the World Bank Group reports that nearly all PSs have not complied with the CMP to the expectation. Instead, PSs have decided to formally adopt only legal-show but fail to implement. Among its findings on the free movement of goods, it reveals that:

“While all Partner States have formally eliminated tariffs on intra-regional trade, measures with equivalent effects remain. For instance, EAC certificates of origin are often not recognized at borders, and none of the PSs have complied with EAC Council’s recommendations to enact domestic legislation imposing penalties on people who furnish false documentation to obtain them. *A/so*, all PSs still apply NTBs, with most related to sanitary and phytosanitary measures, rules of origin, additional taxes and charges, and technical barriers to trade” (EAC and WB, 2014).

On the same footing, *East African Business Council (EABC) Report* (2014) reveals that:

“Multiple Certification Marks (CMs) in the EAC and some PSs consider some CMs, as not approximated to their own marks due to unharmonized conformity assessment infrastructure in the region as such affected their effectiveness in promotion of free movement of goods in the region, because some CMs are not readily accepted in some PSs. Also, there is lack of a monitoring mechanism by the EAC to ensure that the provisions of the Standard Quality, Metrology and Testing Act regarding the adoption and implementation of the EAS are undertaken by PSs.”

These findings are not different as to what the EAC Secretary General Dr. Sezibera and Kenyan Cabinet Secretary for EAC Affairs Phyllis Kandie proclaimed, during the October 2013 forum—“The EAC We Want.” Both vowed on the danger of existing major legal, political, economic and social restrictions on movement of labour, goods, people and services and intra-EAC trade challenges. More surprisingly is that these challenges are the same challenges that prevailed when the EAC–DS was developed in 2011. For instance, the EAC–DS report reported:

“The prevalence of NTBs, inadequate infrastructure; institutional handicaps; inadequate national level capacities to domesticate regional policies; divergent socio-economic structures; supply side constraints; weak legal, regulatory and dispute settlement mechanisms and requisite powers for EAC to enforce Community obligations and decisions; delays in operationalization of EAC competition Act; mismatch during the implementation of trade facilitation instruments and processes are some of the major constraints that slowed the achievement of the full benefits of the EACU and EACM” (EAC, 2011).

These findings suggest what the author does not want to discuss in this paper. However, they give wide range of explanations, some are contradictory. First, is PSs— being motionless, reluctant and incredulous to harmonize their national laws, policies and regulations complying with the CMP. Secondly, the implementation gap between PSs gives unequal sharing of EAC benefits. Lastly, with one year to the deadline, fully implementation of CMP remains a pipedream unless further steps are taken. Therefore it is evident that for the past four years, PSs have demonstrated slow pace of harmonizing national laws, policies and systems in compliance with the CMP.

Truly, the challenges and restrictions reflected within recent research findings are enormous. These directly hamper all efforts set towards the optimistic achievement of the EACM. To move from here, EAC leaders and other stakeholders have to dare to know and learn. After the European Community (EC) negotiated the “*Single European Act*,” what accounted for their success were two things. One is stressing the independent activism of international or transnational actors and the second emphasizing bargaining between leaders (Nelsen and Stubb, 1994). EAC should look at this and counterfeit to get what they want. However, the author suggests that more commitment from PSs is needed. If it happens, then they will set the pace for compliance and appropriate application of rules and regulations as per agreement(s). While this is done, co-operation between PSs, EAC organs and institutions, private sectors and other stakeholders is vitally important, in order to assist in the attainment of ambitious goals of the Community. While doing this, a sharp research for additional information is needed from all discourse to facilitate a way of effecting compliance and implementation of the CMP.

3.1 How do EAC citizens enjoy the freedom and right of establishment and residence?

The right to move free and establish residence in another EAC Partner State is provided under Article 7, 13 and 14 respectively. Under this arrangement, EAC citizens are guaranteed the rights to reside in any Partner State, along with their spouse, dependant and child, for the purpose of living, visiting, touring, transit, education, training, and working. The CMP also encapsulates the right for citizens to establish their business in any PSs and pursue economic activities in accordance with the national laws of the PS. This includes even self-employed persons who are free to carry out their work across the region, and be entitled to social security schemes in the host country. In the enjoyment of these rights and freedom, they are all subjected to limitations justified by PS(s) on grounds of public policy, public security or public health and upon imposing such limitations, PS is obliged to notify the other PSs accordingly.

For the past four years nonetheless, PSs has fully complied with these enshrined rights and freedoms. For instance, Kenya and Rwandan governments have made some improvements including; “waiving off the work permit fees for EAC citizens” (FES, 2012; Ogalo, 2012; EAR, 2013) to allow free movement of labour and persons. Also, the two governments have repealed their immigration laws: “the Kenya Citizenship and Immigration Act No.12 of 2011 and, Kenya Citizens and Foreign Nationals Management Act No.31 of 2011” (Ogalo, 2012; FES, 2013). Rwanda government has put in place new Immigration Law No. 04 / 2011 of 21 / 03 / 2011 , replacing Law No . 17 / 99 of

16/08/1999 on Immigration and Emigration (EAR, 2013). But apart from them, neither Burundi or Tanzania nor Uganda has repealed its Citizenship and Immigration laws in conformity with the CMP.

This vindicates that PSs are ranging behind in effecting such CMP provisions. It is also true to say, some PSs have not been wholehearted by regarding these provisions. For instance, Tanzania was particularly against the aspects of “free movement and rights residence” forming part of the CMP and was only embraced as part of the CMP when consensus was reached to subject it to national laws (Mwapachu, 2012). The argument given by the government has always been that according to the land law Act, Land is public but, vested to the president as custodian on behalf of the citizens. So unlike Tanzania, other EAC PSs land is privately owned and scarce. Therefore, Tanzania fears land grabbing once it fully complies with CMP. It is unfortunate that with all these fallout, the free movement of persons and rights of establishment and residence remain to be what former Secretary General Mwapachu called “nightmare.” In July, 2013, tourism Ministers from the five EAC member states, met in Arusha and outlined new targets for rolling out a common passport and visa by July 2014 as per Article 9 of CMP yet nothing have been done so far. The issue of common passport and visa has been a case since 2005, but, the initiatives have been delayed due to security concerns, poor infrastructure, and disagreements over visa fee schedules and modalities of revenue sharing.

4.0 EAC COMMON MARKET PROSPECTS

For many developing countries, the groupings are proving important grounds for developing their comparative advantage and for enhancing the competitive skills of their enterprises before facing the rigorous task of international competition (Kabbaj, 2003). Salim Ahmed Salim, former Secretary General of Organization of African Unity (OAU) argues on the same line of thinking that, “no single African country however important or well endowed can have any serious impact on a world scale. But the African collective cannot be ignored” (Salim, 2014). One of the reasons is that developing countries like those in Africa have small national economies and fragmented markets compared to others.

Therefore, Salim urges African countries to recognize their individual disadvantages and the merits of co-operation and integration in order inter alia to cope with the present and future challenges and opportunities facing them. It is on this backdrop we turn to discuss the prospects of the EAC–CM. First, it aims to join their efforts together to create a robust market and strong economy before they face the globe. For example, the EAC region market of 141.8 million people has the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of \$100 billion in 2012 compared to South Africa, Venezuela, Czech Republic and Malaysia which had (individually) less population (millions) of 50.6, 29.3, 10.5 and 28.9 but, having extensive GDP (US\$-billions) of 384.3, 382.4, 196.1 and 303.5 respectively (Schwab, 2013). This is why African leaders and other stakeholders are more than ever keen to accelerate economic growth and development of the PSs through the attainment of the free movement of goods, services, capital and labour towards the AEC in an increased inter-REC harmonization and convergence initiatives, such as the COMESA–EAC–SADC tripartite Free Trade Area.

Secondly, aims to increase volume and value of intra-trade and business competition in the region. This is an important aspect altering of the business environment to create competitiveness among the Partners’ enterprises and open up new opportunities for trade and investment that was not in-place before. PSs are expected to eliminate tariffs, NTBs and other technical trade restrictions as per EACU and CMP, to enable exploitation of wonderful opportunities created. Once this is done, it will facilitate product differentiation, economies of scale and quality products, lower and transparent prices as well as change of industries behaviour.

Thirdly, creation of market freedom where there is free movement for factors of production between the member countries. This will facilitate factors of production to be more efficiently allocated, in advance increase productivity within the Community thus enable great completion, market-oriented and sustainable production of goods and services where consumers benefit through cheaper and different products/services. For example, currently Azam industry and Shellys Pharmaceuticals of Tanzania; Madhvani and Mukwano Groups of Uganda; East African Breweries, Cable, BIDCO, Kenya Airways and Kenya Commercial Bank, all of Kenya operate across borders.

Fourthly, Consumers benefit. Despite the challenges, the EAC–CM aims at promoting large and efficient scale production of commodities to suit the intra-regional trade and market. This facilitates consumers’ benefit in the sense that, having the single market resuscitate competitive environment which brings cheaper products, more efficient providers of products/services and also increase choice of products/services. In this respect, competition is expected to stimulate innovations that will bring new and cheap products to consumers. Fifth,, promotes significant growths of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) within the region and technology diffusion from one member country to another.

Last but not least, is harmonization of policies to reduce trade cost and increase production of commodities and services in the region. Article 30 of the CMP articulates that, for the proper functioning of the Common Market PSs shall co-ordinate and harmonizes their economic and monetary policies to ensure macro-economic stability, sustainable economic growth and balanced development. However, this provision in most cases remains impractical as PSs are yet to harmonize taxes: VAT, East African Standards, exercise duties, amongst others, in conformity with the CMP. Moreover, if policies and regulations are harmonized, the Common Market will “create a system of surveillance upon one another based on best endeavors and at the time backed by legal systems” (EAC, 2012). The end results will strengthen massive production of commodities and services with low cost that directly and indirectly benefits citizens.

4.1 EAC Common Market Challenges

In spite of the important prospects of the region, the overall performance of the EAC–CM falls short of the ambitious target. Perhaps, this is what Mwapachu articulates that “in as much as EAC is leading from the front as the REC, its challenges have little to learn from other experiences, neither from other African RECs or Caribbean Economic Community (CARICOM) nor ASEAN (Mwapachu, 2012). However, from the Developmental Integration Theory, point of view, PSs should focus on how to stimulate or create efficient productive and trade capacity in the first place. Therefore, they should not ask where to look at, rather consider creating the first impetus working from the bottom and rebuilding from present entities that are naturally rooted in common interests. Thus, the current challenges which continue to besmirch the economic spur and sustainable development of the region as well as militate against the implementations of the CMP are enormous, requiring a strong commitment, appropriate rules and procedures on how to address them. In the following discussion, we turn to describe the common challenges and limitations that shove the compliance as well as implementation of the CMP to remains pronounced more theoretically than practically.

4.1.1 Lack of political will among PSs

Literally, lack of political will among PSs means that PSs are unwilling or uncommitted to support legal compliance and implementation of the key decisions of the EAC. This concept illustrates a pessimist ideal for negative policy outcomes. The approach on how member states pursue regional agreements and policies follows suit to this. This is why it is obvious in the EAC–CM for PSs to discharge their role retrospectively. For example, the slow pace of the harmonisation and implementation of the CMP demonstrates the strong lack of political will among PSs and thus, creates doubt as if they have changed their stance.

One year to the deadline of implementing EAC–CM (2010-2015), the progress is still very limited. PSs almost key policies are yet to be harmonized. For instance, contrary to the Articles: 6, 7, 13 and 14 of the Protocol which provide for free movement of goods, persons and the right of establishment and residence; to a large extent, they remain unrealistic. There are still critical un-equivalent tariff charges and NTBs including road blocks, corruption, VAT, weighbridge, bureaucracy, standard and unrecognized rules of origin that continue to hamper the situation and thus narrow the scope of doing business.

Similarly, the question of political will has been currently exposed between Tanzania and Rwanda. This came into being, following the Tanzania President, Jakaya Kikwete’s appeals to Rwanda and Ugandan governments in May 2013, to negotiate with the “Democratic Forces for the Liberation of Rwanda” (FDLR) and “Allied Democratic Force” (AFD) rebels respectively as part of efforts to find a lasting peace solution in the Great Lakes Region. Nevertheless, his remarks worked well as the Rwandan Foreign Affairs Minister Louise Mushikiwabo, responded that “they would not negotiate with a terrorist group and demanded an apology” (Fierberg, 2013). Later on, the situation deteriorated following the Rwandese President Paul Kagame’s reply. While delivering a speech on June 10th, he described Kikwete’s advice as “dancing on the mass graves of our people [and therefore,] I kept quiet for the contempt I have for it (FDLR talks) because, I thought it was utter nonsense spoken out of ignorance” (Gahiji, 2013; Muhame, 2013). With these “war of words,” the question of political will, sovereignty and psychological warfare triggered between the two countries. First, on July 25th, 2013, the President of Tanzania ordered all illegal aliens to leave in two weeks lest, security and defense organs force them to do so. The eviction took place where Congolese, Burundians, Rwandans and Ugandans left for their homes. Aliens who remained after the given due-time were forced to leave. Secondly, following this repatriation, in August, the government of Rwanda announced the plan with Uganda of withdrawing their businesses from the Dar es Salaam Port which took effect on September 1st. Thirdly, on September 2nd, Rwanda slapped a new road toll fee from \$152 to \$500 only on Tanzanian trucks transporting goods and services through Rusumo-border to Kigali-Rwanda. However, after the two governments negotiated, the new charge was withdrawn.

More surprisingly, we saw the so-called “coalition-of-willing” banking on article 7(1e) of the EAC Treaty. Under this roof, three consecutive meetings (June-Entebbe, August-Mombasa and October-Kigali) were held in absence of Burundi and Tanzania. In these meetings, participants agreed, amongst other things, on the establishment of Single Customs Territory; developing Mombasa-Kampala-Kigali railway; use of Single regional Identity Cards and Tourist Visa rather than the East African or National Passports for intra - EAC travel and fast - track the political federation. As this creates grievance, Tanzania responded, through the Minister for EAC Co-operation Samwel Sitta, that; “So long as they have consciously decided to isolate us, we wish them well but, Tanzania will not recognise any wrecker decision.” Therefore all the above statements prove the danger of political will that may turn the Community’s dream to vanish. However, with all these scramble and squash, the East African Court of Justice (EACJ) did not intervene since, Article 32 (b) of the Treaty gridlocks the Court jurisdiction as it shall hear and determine dispute if the dispute is submitted to it under a special agreement between the PSs concerned. Therefore, unlike the European Court of Justice that plays an executive role within the union, EACJ jurisdiction is ousted.

To many of us, more questions than answers were raised. One of the questions was, is this the beginning of the end of EAC as one of 1977? Conventionally, these dynamics sparked new diplomatic tennis game that continues to be played in an atmosphere of suspicion and thus they have negative implications for the Community’s future. It seems our leaders ignored that the EAC–CM rules required their concern, commitment and active role when it comes to the implementation. In fact, the principle of “variable geometry” under article 7(1e) allows PSs to undertake only special-interest activities that are not in the regional plans and inform others through Secretariat in Arusha. However, this was not done. Instead mistrust principle deemed among PSs hence stalled some crucial activities of the Community. So, while AU celebrates its 50th Anniversary and looks forward to continental economic integration, the question for political unwillingness remains stalling the process.

Undoubtedly, this is why, Juma Mwapachu argues that; “The legal landscape is an important integral part of EAC’s institutional setting in which the integration process takes place. Institutions begin to degenerate when crucial decisions start being taken outside legally constituted frameworks” (Mwapachu, 2013). The Community must empower its institutions in order to be able to make and implement its decision than as being dictated by member states. Therefore, PSs should learn their mistakes and grow from them to avoid ruining the Community’s good history of unity and solidarity.

4.1.2 The issue of state sovereignty

Sovereignty is a Westphalian concept that according to Nnoli (1986) means, “the capacity of a ruling class to make and implement decisions which are of interest to it.” This definition suits our discussion whereby the compliance and implementation of the CMP are undermined by PSs under the umbrella of states sovereignty. Gerhard Erasmus, (2009), believes that “the endeavour to liberalise trade faces two traditional challenges: the sovereignty of states, and the fact that governments, as a rule, do not trade.” To him, states exercise jurisdiction over their own territory and over commercial transactions concluded on their soil, but, trade is not predominately an inter-governmental matter. This fact remarks what East African-PSs governments are inclined to, through opting for compromise politics in the region. Therefore, to pull back the move for EAC–CM requires PSs to respect their obligations and to establish active follow-up measures in order to ensure specific outcomes. Also, national measures from all organs of the government should work in a tandem with regional measures to ensure comprehensive plans of implementing the CMP. That is to say, EAC needs strong supranational-regimes for common functions than the inter-governmental approach.

4.1.3 Language barrier

Language is used by human beings as a means of communication with one another. However, in the EAC, there is no unifying language which is either spoken or used for different purposes unanimously (regional-wise) by all citizens and PS governments. Article 137 of the Treaty postulates that, “the official language of the Community shall be English and Kiswahili shall be developed as a lingua franca of the Community” (EAC, 1999). In addition, in November, 2013, we saw the summit of Heads of States directing the Council of Ministers to study the modalities of including French as a language of the Community. This gives legitimacy to the Community as English, French or Swahili speakers. Nevertheless, the reality reveals that neither of the country within the Community speaks or uses all three languages as official languages. More ridiculously, it is only Kenya where majority of its citizens can communicate through English and Swahili languages. In Tanzania and Uganda, majority can communicate in Swahili and English respectively with their indigenous languages; meanwhile, in Rwanda and Burundi, the majority speak/share Kinyarwanda/Kirundi and French. Therefore, if we want to facilitate free movement of people, market, trade and economic integration in the region, we must have the unifying language as the Community Economic Monetary of Central Africa (CEMAC)-French and Arab Maghreb Union (AMU)-Arabic. It is impossible for all the three languages to be mastered as per needs.

4.1.4 Slow harmonization of PSs laws, policies and systems

For effective and efficient implementation of the CMP, there must be strong commitment for PSs to harmonize national laws, policies and systems beyond national interests in compliance with the Common Market document as per Article 47 of the Protocol. However, for the past three years, the article rests unrealistically. PSs are yet to domesticate even half of the arrangements into national policies, laws, systems and regulations hence, this outnumbers all achievements that have been reached so far. For example, neither of the member states has ratified the “EAC Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures Protocol” (EAC and WB, 2014). Thus, to the moment, a number of issues remain outstanding including imposition of legal NTBs, effective application of CET, domestic tax charges, including income tax and VAT, no mutual recognition of rule of origin, amongst others. PSs should be clear to adopt critical domestic measures and policies for establishing regional legal regimes that makes it easier for trade to take place and to dismantle the obstacles that prevent the free flow of goods.

4.1.5 Poor infrastructure

In Africa and EAC in particular, transport and communication infrastructures cost for quite long have a detrimental effect on trade, investment and general flow of information from one member state to another. Nevertheless, although road transport in Africa seems to be a key means of trade, as alternative modes of transport are either inefficient (railways) or too expensive (air transport) (Ancharaz et al., 2011), in EAC, things are different. Its roads are less-paved and the whole bloc is not connected by paved roads while their “density is less than 7 kilometers per 100 sq. km. of land, the lowest in the world” (Ibid). This first, makes infrastructure systems to remain too expensive if one wants to travel or transit goods/services from one part of the EAC to another. As, President Museveni noted: “it costs about US\$ 4,000 to transport a 40-ft container from Hong Kong to Mombasa, while it costs about US\$ 10,000 to transport the same container to Bujumbura from Mombasa. The use of the wrong mode of transport – trucks (by Road) instead of Railway – contributes 35-50 % to this high cost” (Museveni, 2012). Thus, PS should re-double their efforts to improve hard and soft infrastructure. This will unlock intra-regional trade bottleneck and widen trade leading to economic spur of the region. But, if these challenges remain, then, they will continue to undermine the spirit of free movement, market and trade of the region, while also contributing to price fluctuations and consequently, affix cost of production for producers, increase cost of transport for suppliers before creating burden to the last consumers. In the access of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), it indicates inadequate growing in the region. We should improve this area too.

Other challenges include low public awareness across the community, bureaucracy and corruption. There is a great need for providing potential civic education to all East African citizens. This will mobilise and raise civic awareness of the citizens, to understand the importance and philosophy of the Community towards building new spirits for the future generation. In the case of bureaucracy and corruption, there are still excessive bureaucracy, regulation and corruption that weaken the smooth running of business in the region. The prolonged bureaucratic systems and corrupt practices within the PSs thwart and delay the performance of the EAC–CM arrangements. Except in Rwanda, in other PSs, it seems easier for anyone to bribe an officer than to follow all bureaucratic systems. PSs should agree and implement better ways out on how to foster the rule of law, transparency and accountability for state(s) organs and regional administrations to function to save for the region.

5.0 EAC COMMON MARKET REFORMS

Making the Common Market work to the expectations requires a higher degree of commitment. PSs should be committed to ratify, domesticate and implement several of agreements agreed. Bela Balassa writing in 1961 and reprinted by Nelsen and Stubb (1994) reminds us that:

“A higher form of economic integration is attained in a common market, where not only trade restrictions but, also restrictions of factor of movements are abolished. An economic union, as distinct from a common market, combines the suppression of restrictions on commodity and factor policies, in order to remove discrimination that was due to disparities in these policies. Finally, total economic integration presupposes ...the setting-up of a supranational authority whose decisions are binding for the member states.”

From this ground however, much has been done in the EAC but, it still faces enormous challenges. It cannot ignore this, all it can do is to re-work them more for the better future. What lacks here is a strong degree of commitment which is shown when signing these agreements and thus, affects the pace for the implementation. To this point, the major question before us is what steps and how will EAC take to resolve these thorny issues?

In the *African competitiveness Report 2013*, the authors spotlight again: corruption, inefficiency of government bureaucracy, access to financing; inadequate supply of infrastructure; Tax rates, regulation and Inflation as the most problematic factors for doing business within East African countries (WEF, 2013). This has consequently led the region to continue suffering from economic disparity and marginalization in spite of its abundant natural resources. The author thinks, the Community may start from here. First and foremost, Member states are pre-supposed to agree to adopt legal instruments, common policies and common institutions in critical areas to match with the regional Treaty, Protocols and other arrangements. This should go along with making domestic reforms that will be able to adopt comprehensive policies as effort is made to oversee regional agreements. Therefore, regional PSs need to think, plan and implement as a region to ensure the entire impediment factors before them are minimized to the highest extent possible.

For example, for effective application of CET, PSs should consider creating a grand free trade area as that of COMESA-EAC-SADC Tripartite framework which includes all PSs. But, some exception for Burundi is required. This is because, Burundi as a member of the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS) fails legally to comply with the CET. However, if the ambition is to create Pan-African Economic Community (Pan-AEC) by 2028, ECCAS may therefore be invited to participate in the free COMESA-EAC-SADC Tripartite and finally merge to free COMESA-EAC- ECCAS-SADC Tripartite framework. PSs should work on solidarity principles to share and exchange their knowledge, skills and experience in tackling major predicaments. This will facilitate and foster meticulous economic integration as well as sustainable development of the region.

Secondly, there is the need for amending the EAC Treaty Articles 6(a) and 7(1e) to clearly re-define the regional meaning of the Articles, as well as the CMP example Articles 7(5-6) and 13(8-9) that restrict free movement of persons. The amendment of these documents should focus not only on how to abolish persons and trade restrictions but, also to make them binding for the member states and empower more EAC Secretariat to act accordingly as CEMAC where the Commission executes their functions independently and are guided by the general interest of the Community. Thirdly, the Community should have common institutions and enforcement mechanisms to enforce its decisions, policies, and programmes. These should be strengthened and empowered with the necessary powers and resources to enable them discharge their respective mandates effectively and independently at regional and national levels. The current institutions like East African Legislative Assembly, EACJ and Secretariat do not have full mandates of their own rather than being dictated and symbolic. For example, Articles 33(1) and 54(2) of the Treaty and the CMP respectively oust the jurisdiction of the EACJ to settle disputes between PSs into national courts. Hence issues of political will, inaction, delay, and ineffectiveness in the implementation of the region decisions can easily prevail. EAC needs proactive, independent and strong institutions in the region than strong-men.

Fourthly, for the future progress and development of the region, Swahili language should be more popularized and declared as the official language over other foreign languages. For instance, the Ugandan effort to introduce Swahili as the national language and in the academic curriculum where all primary pupils are taught is an impressive result and stepping stone whereby other PSs: Burundi and Rwanda should follow suit for the full unification of the region. Fifth, the Heads of State and individual personalities within the Community should put aside their emotional, personal differences and grievances when it comes to the region's interests. They should show maturity and come together to sort out their differences and misunderstandings for the interest and betterment of the Community.

Sixth, the current stand-off between Tanzania-Rwanda; Uganda-Kenya on rice and sugar exports and other political-economic alliances going-on within the region on the similar agenda of the Community while side-lining other PSs, should be strongly discouraged to enable involvement of all member countries. The fact that some decisions, actions and measures are taken contrary to the agenda of the region raises serious questions about EAC's future impression in its current form. And this weakens all integration efforts put in place and some member states may become untrustworthy and uncommitted to the agendas of the region. Seventh, there is a need for campaigns regional-wise to build and sensitize public awareness on the vision and mission of the Community. This process will definitely promote as well as provide adequate civic education to all identified programmes, projects and common historical heritages of the integration being properly communicated to the people of the EAC. Eighth, the Community should improve its transport and communication systems in order to reduce economic distance, expand market access and competitiveness, increase trade, investment and promote free movement of people and labour within the Community.

Ninth, there should be systematic and comprehensive coordination, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the regional programmes and projects to ensure the continuation of good spirit of the integration. Encouragement on the consistent and periodic reporting on the progress of the regions' programmes is much desired for the evolution of the integration. This will rehabilitate, resuscitate and foster member states to continue abiding with the Protocol arrangements. Tenth, PSs should abide to harmonize their national policies, laws and regulations to comply with the Protocol. As well as, they should cede their sovereignty over to the supranational organization for effective execution of its mandates and activities. This will help in the efficient and effective implementation of the

Community decisions and lessen the tendency in which PSs may favour national interests over supranational interest. Lastly but not least, Kenya as a strong and greatest economic power in the region has to play a pivotal role in paving for the unification of the EAC. It should voluntarily accept to be a paymaster of the region and bear responsibility of trade imbalance whenever it happens within the Community as per Germany in EU; Brazil in NAFTA and South Africa in SADC. The politics about equal distribution of benefits among member countries cannot be often equally maintained as some members are poorer while others are richer.

6.0 CONCLUSION

EAC is a crucial regional grouping not only to the East African countries but, also for the whole continent towards the achievement of the Pan-AEC and African unity as well. Therefore, we must first clearly think of the economic integration by making Customs Union and Common Market work as the key hearts of the economic Community that directly benefit the citizens. In fact, since the basic document of the region in creating free market and trade is the CMP, PSs should re-examine their move towards goal(s) asserted. The assertion that, the EAC–CM may be fully implemented because PSs have signed and ratified the Protocol requires re-assessment. This is because, for the past four years of operation, the CMP has accurately remained theoretical than practical. Low political will and state sovereignty are real detrimental effects for the implementation of regional arrangement. The author's closer examination and other scholarly writings, assessment and government reports reveal that the challenges and limitations ahead were beyond optimist expectations when the CMP was signed.

Therefore, although there are low records of achievements in relation to the lofty aspiration of the Community, the prospects remain inspiring to all people of East Africa. The challenges we face are enormous and undeniable, but hopes, opportunities and prospects are evident too for the successful and integrated market in the region. Thus, there should be active participation from all level(s) namely; individuals, governments, private sectors, civil societies and other important stakeholders. PSs should rethink and make hard decisions to walk their talks for the development of the region. It can be done, get up, unite to comply and struggle for full implementation of the CMP and the future economic union of Africa.

COMPETING INTEREST

No Competing Interest

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